

Chinese Esoteric Buddhism (Tang Tantrism)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Tantric school (mi zong 密宗 or mi jiao 密教)

Before mid-Tang, numerous texts containing Buddhist tantric practices and mantra had arrived in China and they were translated into Chinese. But the systematic and more particular version Esoteric Buddhism did not appear until Emperor Xuanzong's reign. Three Indian Tantric masters Śubhakarasiṃha (善無畏), Vajrabodhi (金剛智) and Amoghavajra (不空), brought the Esoteric Buddhist (later known in Japan as Zhenyan 真言, "true word", "mantra") tradition from 716 to 720 during the reign of Emperor Xuanzong. Tantra/Esoteric Buddhism that has spread in Tang China and was transmitted to Japan during the same period via two famous masters Kukai (空海) and Saicho (最澄). This tradition highly depended on mandalas, mantras, mudras, abhiṣekas, and deity yoga, containing magical rituals, spells, and other elements also seen in other Indian religions. Gradually this systematic tradition died out in China after the destruction of Buddhism during the Wuzong period (846). Later during the Song, more Esoteric Buddhist texts were brought to the Song court and translated, but their influence was incomparable to Tang tantric Buddhism. However, various elements and practices still existed in Chan and Pure Land Buddhism in China until today. Scattered records in Song and Ming dynasties show that certain mantric practices including Uṣṇiṣa vijaya dhāraṇī sūtra and Vajra Krodha Mahābala Ucchuṣma were still secretly practiced by some practitioners.

Date Range: 716 CE - 900 CE

Region: Western Shaanxi

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

Western Shaanxi and northern China. But also transmitted in southern China in Guangzhou and Zhejiang

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Robert Sharf. "Lun Hanchuan mijiao 论汉传密教" [On Chinese Esoteric Buddhism], trans. Zhang Linghui 张凌晖, in *Hewei mijiao? Guanyu mijiao de dingyi, xiuxi, fuhao he lishi de quanshi yu zhenglun 何谓密教? 关于密教的定义、修习、符号和历史的诠释与争论* [What is Esoterism? On the Interpretation and Controversy over the Definition, Practice, Semiology, and Historiography of Esoterism], edited by Shen Weirong 沈卫荣 (Beijing: Zhongguo zang xue, 2013), pp. 114-142.
- Source 2: Yael Bentor and Meir Shahar. *Chinese and Tibetan Esoteric Buddhism*. Leiden: Brill, 2017.
- Source 3: Orzech, Charles D. (general editor) (2011). *Esoteric Buddhism and the Tantras in East Asia*. Brill.

Notes: Payne, Richard K. (2006). *Tantric Buddhism in East Asia*. Wisdom Publications. Geoffrey C. Goble. (2019). *Chinese Esoteric Buddhism: Amoghavajra, the Ruling Elite, and the Emergence of a Tradition*. New York: Columbia University Press. Michelle C. Wang. (2018). *Manḍalas in the Making: The Visual Culture of Esoteric Buddhism at Dunhuang*. Leiden: Brill.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/view/document/obo-9780195393521/obo-9780195393521-0183.xml>
- Notes: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/kukai/> <https://www.encyclopedia.com/religion/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/mijiao-esoteric-school>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/mobile/index.php?index=T>
- Source 1 Description: Chinese Tripitaka collection which contain major scriptures and sources on Tang tantrism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Recent research has shown that Tantrici Buddhism was heavily influenced by and had influenced Hinduism rituals and cosmology. In Tang China, the interaction between Tantric Buddhist rituals and practices and religious Daoism is also visible. Evidence kept in Dunhuang showed that in Inner Asia Tantric Buddhism absorbed various kinds of local religions and beliefs. Moreover, recent studies have shown that the Northern Chan Buddhist communities had interacted with Tang tantric

masters.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shaanxi and Northern China in general

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Esoteric Buddhism highly emphasises the dharma lineage succession process, and achieved masters must conduct a series of esoteric ritual process to pass on his or her dharma lineage to qualified disciples. This ritual is known as abhiṣeka (guanding 灌頂), a path through which the recipient could receive both mystical empowerment of specific Buddhist deities as well as the legitimate dharma lineage from a Vajrayana master.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: It is hard to say whether the reception of guanding is a personal choice or not. But this process does require active and full devotion of the disciple and his or her absolute trust in both the master and the Buddhist deities. Disciples are expected to actively choose to follow the esoteric path at the initial stage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Unlike early Brahman religion which was strictly limited to certain castes, Esoteric Buddhist guanding is open to anyone suitable to this practice. But esoteric masters have the total right to make this kind of decisions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Assigned by gender:

— No

Notes: Not only that Esoteric Buddhism was open to both gender, but the boundary between the monastic and laity was also not very strict in Tang China, which is different from the Japanese Shingon tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

— Yes

Notes: Guanding is a particular kind of secretive ritual that is seen in many different kind of mahayana texts, but institutionalised in Esoteric texts. It imitates the ancient Indian kings' coronation bathing ritual. Guanding is the crucial ritual in esoteric practices.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

— Yes [specify]: Level of cultivation verified by the masters.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— Yes

Notes: Esoteric Buddhism in its transmission in Tang China actively proselytize to the imperial court and high elites, and this tradition also attracted a significant number of elite monks. Prominent patriarchs often perform miraculous rituals and superpowers to attract believers and supporters. Based on extant records, we can see that certain specific rituals and spells were not "esoteric" in nature and available to anyone who had faith in their power without the Guanding initiation. But systematic practice must be initiated by the Guanding ritual.

Does the religion have official political support

— Yes

Notes: In the Tang Empire, Esoteric Buddhist communities were supported and sponsored by emperors and political elites. Important temples in Changan and Luoyang became centres of Esoteric Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

— Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

— Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

— No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

— No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

— Yes

Notes: Many Esoteric rituals related to the protection of the state or the benefit of the emperor or even praying for rain in draughted seasons are enforced by the Tang state as regular imperial ritual performance.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

— Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The samaya vows are the most important precepts bestowed to the initiates of Esoteric Buddhism in the guanding ritual, which includes a set of rules and restrictions for a practitioner to follow (monastic and lay). If the samaya vows are partially damaged or completely violated, then the religious integrity of a practitioner is broken and she or he is no longer a fully qualified Esoteric follower anymore. Only by a series of repentance practices that the damage could be repaired, but some sins are considered unreparable.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: It is believed that the violation of samaya vows will automatically cause certain negative consequences. But there is not official punishment. A breacher is expected to repent her sins by herself in front of Buddhist deities and masters until certain auspicious signs show up to prove that the violation is repaired.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to count the exact or even a rough number of the followers of Esoteric Buddhism in Tang dynasty. But we can assume that at its peak this religious teaching was very influential among social elites in China based on various records.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - No
 - ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - No
 - No
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - No
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Esoteric elements appeared in numerous Buddhist texts translated into Chinese before the 8th century. But the type of Esoteric practices brought by the famous three masters during the Kaiyuan period in Tang are derived from two specific scriptures translated into Chinese in the 8th century, Vajraśekhara Sūtra (known as Jingang dingjing 金剛頂經) and Mahāvairocana Tantra (known as Dari jing 大日經). Other tantric sutras were also translated along with these two scriptures. During the Song dynasty, Indian Esoteric monks Devaśāntika (Tianxi zai 天息災) and Dānapāla (Shihu 施護) brought and translated more Esoteric sutras but their influence was limited.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Both Dari jing and Jingang dingjing, and other tantric texts were translated into classical Chinese and originally written on scrolls. Some pieces of their sanskrit versions are discovered (see

https://www.academia.edu/4473437/A_Sanskrit_Manuscript_of_the_Sarvabuddhasamāyogaḍākīnījālaśaṃvara_Handout_for_Manuscripta_

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The majority of esoteric Buddhist scriptures attributed to the Buddha's emanation body (baoshen 報身) or the dharma body (fashen 法身), the Mahāvairocana Buddha (Dari rulai 大日如來 or Pulu zhena fo 毗盧遮那佛). It is believed that these sutras and rituals are told by Mahāvairocana Buddha and transmitted to the human realm by Buddha's empowerment. Some sutras are attributed to Śākyamuni himself as an incarnation of Mahāvairocana Buddha. There is no clear narrative of the origin of these esoteric scriptures but only what is told in the texts. Some Chinese legends ascribe the discovery of these scriptures to Nāgārjuna Bodhisattva, but there has been no Indian sources to verify these legends so far.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the temples related to Esoteric Buddhism in Tang empire had been destroyed. But Buddhist caves in Dunhuang and Dazu 大足 in Chongqing province contain significant amount of Esoteric themes and elements. Apart from Esoteric relics in Dunhuang, carves and statues in Dazu show that until the beginning of the Song, Esoteric practices were still transmitted in southwestern China.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Tombs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- All public spaces

Notes: Iconography is vital in Esoteric practices especially in many visualisation rituals. practitioners are expected to offer ritual sacrifices and visualise the image of their selected "True Veneration" deity (benzun 本尊) day and night in order to receive the deity's empowerment. Therefore, visual images of these True Veneration deities are present in many occasions for public worship and secretive rituals.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The visual features of Esoteric Buddhist iconography is a very complex topic and cannot be easily concluded in a few words. These image icons in China combined Indian and Central Asian religious art motives with Chinese Buddhist visual traditions, and transformed different kinds styles and features to express specific Esoteric doctrines and teachings. Please consult Matthew T. Kapstein and Sam van Schaik, (2010), *Esoteric Buddhism at Dunhuang: Rites and Teachings for This Life and Beyond*, Leiden: Brill, and MC Wang's book at the beginning of the entry.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: Like other Mahayana Buddhist beliefs, Esoteric Buddhism advocates the homogeneity between mind and body.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Like other Buddhist traditions, Esoteric Buddhism also advocates the reincarnation of life in the six sentient being realms (ṣaḍ-gaṭi). This belief is sometimes visualised as bhavacakra in both Chinese and Tibetan Esotericism.
 - ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Deva (heavenly being) realm is considered "above" the human realm and other realms.
 - ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
 - Yes [specify]: The realm of the Gods (Devas) in different heavens, the realm of demigods and fighting demons (Asura) in their deep ocean palaces, the realm of human being, the realm of an the realm of hungry ghosts, the realm of hell beings

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

- ↳ In a human form:
 - Yes
- ↳ In animal/plant form:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Only in sentient animal form.
- ↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
 - No
- ↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
 - No
- ↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Chinese Esoteric Buddhism also agree with the general Buddhist notion of karma (ye 業), the law of cause and effect initiated by individual life's mind and ignorance.
- ↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:
 - Yes [specify]: The realm of Asura and the realm of an the realm of hungry ghosts are also believed as part of "this world" which are in the same dimension with human beings and animals.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

- ↳ Cremation:
 - Yes

Notes: Like other Chinese Buddhist schools and patriarchs, Chinese Esoteric masters in the Tang also received the jhāpita ritual (Tupi 荼毗). Dead monks' bodies were burnt and put into a tower shrine in temples and worshipped as a sacred site. According to Śubhakarasiṃha's inscribed epitaph, his body was put into the tower shrine in Guanghua Temple. (See 大唐東都大聖善寺故中天竺國善無畏三藏和尚碑銘并序)
- ↳ Mummification:
 - Yes
- ↳ Interment:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cannibalism:
 - No
- ↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Feeding to animals:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Secondary burial:
 - No
- ↳ Re-treatment of corpse:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
 - Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:
— Yes [specify]: Buddhist treasures and ornaments.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Other grave goods:
— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Are formal burials present:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Normally as an official routine, the body relics of an achieved Esoteric master is "invited" into a tower shrine, with incense burning ceremonies and offerings. After this formal ritual, the tower is sealed and should not be open again unless extreme events happen.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

— Yes

Notes: "Supernatural" is not a concept applicable to Esoteric Buddhist teachings or any Mahayana Buddhist traditions in China. All myriad beings are believed as temporarily existing in a complex realm called "Dharma Realm" (fajie 法界). This Dharma Realm is the foundation and platform for both sentient beings, the material universe, Buddha's pure lands and Buddhahood itself to manifest themselves. In this sense, heavenly gods, ghosts, hell beings are all believed as "natural beings", since the distinction between nature and supernature does not exist. Therefore, the only "natural" mode of existence is not the mode comprehensible to human beings but only to the enlightened ones. In this sense, only Buddha could thoroughly understand and perceive Dharma Realm since Buddha's ignorance is completely eliminated and Buddha's wisdom transcends all kinds of duality. However, this perfect image of Buddha is not simply ascribed to Śākyamuni himself. Esoteric Buddhist tradition venerates Buddha's more superior, secretive and powerful form Mahāvairocana (Dari rulai 大日如来), whom ordinary sentient beings cannot see or understand. This is Buddha's perfect and true "dharma body", and Śākyamuni is only considered as one of trillions of Mahāvairocana's incarnations. According to Chinese Esoteric scriptures, Mahāvairocana represents the true dharma of all beings, and this dharma body of Buddha is present in every time and space. It is synonymous to Dharma Realm.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

— Yes

Notes: Mahāvairocana is considered as the most superior one, and all heavenly gods, Bodhisattvas and sentient beings are Mahāvairocana's subordinates. But this idea of a supreme being is different from that of Christianity in that Mahāvairocana as the dharma body of Buddha is the result of Buddha's long cultivation in different cycles of life. It is an achievement that any sentient being could attain once converted to Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

— Yes

Notes: In Chinese Esoteric tradition, Mahāvairocana is visualised in anthropomorphic style, but this human form is only considered as a vision (convenient way) to guide human beings. The true body of Mahāvairocana has no form, no limit and no boundaries.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

— No

Notes: Mahāvairocana Buddha and Buddha's disciple-Bodhisattvas and subordinates are believed to reside in the inner court of the highest level of rūpa-dhātu, the heaven of pure form (sejie tian 色界天). But Buddha and Buddha's dependents are not considered as deva gods who directly intervene with human affairs and hold the responsibility of managing the cosmos and who are sentient beings in samara themselves. In fact, some texts claim that Mahāvairocana Buddha is seen as the "dharma lord" of a series of cosmos and everything is seen as a part of Buddha's body.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

— No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Yes [specify]: Mahāvairocana is the supreme Buddha for worship. According to Esoteric teachings, any offering and pray to Mahāvairocana could in return initiate Buddha's empowerment and guidance. Therefore, any practitioner especially Esoteric patriarch and patrons should loyally dedicate to the practice of Mahāvairocana.
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Mahāvairocana is believed to be omniscient
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Yes [specify]: By certain meditative methods and spells, esoteric practitioners in theory could conjure and communicate with spirits and ghosts
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at

home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Depend on which samara realm a so-called supernatural being resides in, they could have completely different understandings and perceptions about the same object, phenomenon or geographic location.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Ghosts, demigods, heavenly beings, hell beings can all possess certain kinds of emotions like human beings and sometimes even more intense.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
 - Yes [specify]: Political affairs and natural phenomena

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Only through monarch:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Yes [specify]: Incarnation
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

- ↳ **Supernatural beings care about taboos:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ **Food:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ **Sacred space(s):**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ **Sacred object(s):**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ **Supernatural beings care about other:**
 - Yes [specify]: Morality of the adherents
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ **Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ **Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ **Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ **Supernatural beings care about sex:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ **Adultery:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ **Incest:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi
 - ↳ **Other sexual practices:**
 - Yes [specify]: Homosexuality and impure sexual misconduct of monks.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: There is no idea of "punishment" in a dualistic moral sense, but certain behaviours of bad karma and the violation of esoteric vows will automatically cause punitive results as a consequence of karmic chains. Moreover, some deities of dharma protection will cast curse and punishment on transgressive practitioners, but this is not considered a moral punishment by Buddha.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Western Shanxi
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Empowerment of Buddhas, Bodhisattvas and subordinate deities can result in the enlightenment of one's heart, rebirth in specific Buddha's pure land, and numerous worldly benefits including but not limited to the longevity of life, increase of wealth, strengthening family, miraculous power, etc. Esoteric teachings particularly emphasise the importance of "Fire Sacrifice/Offering" (Homa 護摩) to Buddhas, Bodhisattvas and deities in order to receive such empowerment. Although this looks similar to Brahman rituals, Homa as a form of ritual offering is also widely seen in other Mahayana texts. But esoteric teachings contain very specific procedures of such kind of rituals unique to this tradition.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: All Buddhas incarnate themselves in the sentient beings' dimension for only one purpose: to rescue all sentient beings from the suffering in reincarnation and to guide them to attain (or return to) Buddhahood.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - No
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ Other survival condition:
 - Yes [specify]: Only a small group of person with or without Buddhist or Esoteric belief will survive the Buddhist End of Dharma era and start new cycles of human civilization with better and better morality before Maitreya descends to the human realm to attain Buddhahood.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– Only specialized religious class
– Only one gender
Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– No

↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– No
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

- Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Only for monastic members. But when practicing certain types of rituals or spells, there are ascetic rules for both the monastic and the lay during the practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Unlike Tibetan Esoteric tradition, most of the religious texts of Tang Esoteric teachings emphasises the abstention of sexual behaviour as a necessary condition for the reception of benzun's empowerment. A clean and pure body is prerequisites in many Esoteric rituals. For monastic figures it is absolute since Esoteric or not, Buddhist monastic disciplines requires celibacy. For the lay, fasting is also encouraged during meditative practices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - No
- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - Yes
- ↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other sexual constraints (females):
 - Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: In specific cases, not as a strict doctrine.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Vegetarianism is preferred and highly praised.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Yes

Notes: Not required but happened to devout masters and practitioners.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– I don't know

|

↳ Other:
– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Western Shanxi

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— Yes

Notes: The majority of Chinese Esoteric Buddhist texts are translated into Chinese. However, spells are either transliterated from Sanskrit into Chinese characters with similar pronunciations (in the Tang dynasty) or remained in Sanskrit. Knowledge on the written style and meaning of Sanskrit alphabets and spells are restricted to professionals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

— Yes

Notes: Esoteric calendar-making technique, Indian and Central Asian astronomy and astrology were transmitted into China along with the arrival of Esoteric Buddhism. Originally, specific way of understanding the cosmos and organizing calendars in the Esoteric Buddhist framework might have existed in India. Relevant knowledge was further merged with Chinese local astronomical as well as astrological traditions. In this process, the well-known Chinese Esoteric Buddhist patriarch and astrologist Yixing 一行 (683-727CE) hugely improved Chinese astronomical techniques and the accuracy of traditional Chinese calendar with imported Esoteric Buddhist skills and cosmology.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Western Shanxi

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

— Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: **Western Shanxi**

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **Western Shanxi**

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

— Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: **Western Shanxi**